

Cardinal Number of an Infinite Set Equals to That of Its Power Set?

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Introduction

In sciences, especially Mathematics, a common method to prove a statement, “if **P** then **Q**,” is to assume it is not true or the opposite first and then show it ends with a contradictory statement by deduction. This proof by contradiction is a very efficacious and useful method especially when the statement has finite possibilities, such as either true or false as in most of the cases. Many theorems or theories have been successfully proved by implementing this method. However, this way of proof might be questionable when it is involved in an infinite domain and does not have a clear exclusive true or false choice.

Cantor’s Proof of Cardinality

An example was the proof of the theorem that the cardinal number of a set is always smaller than that of its power set by George Cantor. For example, the cardinal number of the power set of the set of all natural numbers, $\mathbf{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, is greater than that of \mathbf{N} .

Cantor’s proof starts by assuming the opposite, i.e. $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{A})$, the power set of any set \mathbf{A} , has the same cardinal number as that of \mathbf{A} . If this is true, there must exist at least a 1:1 and onto function, \mathbf{f} , from \mathbf{A} to $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{A})$. Cantor has then demonstrated that it is impossible to find an onto function that maps \mathbf{A} to $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{A})$ by finding that a “bad subset” $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{A})$ always exists such that no element in \mathbf{A} can be mapped to \mathbf{B} by any function \mathbf{f} . The “bad subset” \mathbf{B} is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{B} = \{y \mid y \in \mathbf{A} \text{ and } y \notin \mathbf{f}(y)\}$$

i.e. $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{A})$ contains all elements of which each one does not belong to its own image under function \mathbf{f} . Thus, no element $x \in \mathbf{A}$ such that $\mathbf{f}(x) = \mathbf{B}$ can exist even if $\mathbf{B} = \emptyset$, the empty set.

The proof seems to be true for all functions, 1:1 or not. However, an issue may occur when f is 1:1 and every element of $P(A)$ except B can be mapped from an element of A . That is,

$f: A \rightarrow P(A) - B$ is 1:1 and onto.

This is possible when A is infinite. Thus, the cardinal number of A is equal to that of $P(A) - B$. Since $P(A)$ is also infinite, $P(A)$ and $P(A) - B$ have the same cardinal number, implying that the cardinal numbers of $P(A)$ and A are the same!

Direct Proof Contradictory to Cantor's

As a matter of fact, one can easily construct 1:1 and onto functions, g 's, that map $P(A)$ to proper subsets of an infinite set A . Using the set of all natural numbers, N , as an examples without losing generality, one can construct 1:1 functions, g 's, as follows:

$g: P(N) \rightarrow N$

$g(\emptyset) = 1$, and

$g(\{a, b, c, \dots\}) = t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots$, where $a, b, c, \dots \in N$, and t is any natural number greater than 1.

A function g , as defined above, is 1:1 and onto a proper subset of N . Therefore, the cardinal number of $P(N)$ is less than or equal to that of N , opposite to the conclusion proved by Cantor.

Discussion

It is possible to define an inverse function, g^{-1} as follows:

$g^{-1}: g(P(N)) \rightarrow P(N)$,

$g^{-1}(1) = \emptyset$, and

$g^{-1}(t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots) = \{a, b, c, \dots\}$, where $a, b, c, \dots \in N$, and t is any natural number greater than 1.

In this case, the "bad subset" B is N itself. That is, no number $n = t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots \in N$ exists such that

$$g^{-1}(t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots) = N, \text{ or } \{a, b, c, \dots\} = N.$$

The reason is because $n = t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots$ is always greater than any number of $\{a, b, c, \dots\}$, and there is no more “greater number” when $\{a, b, c, \dots\} = N$.

This is consistent with what Cantor has proved. To resolve this issue, one can reconstruct function g as follows:

$$g : P(N) \rightarrow N$$

$$g(\emptyset) = 1,$$

$$g(N) = t + 1, \text{ and}$$

$$g(\{a, b, c, \dots\}) = t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots, \text{ where } a, b, c, \dots \in N, \text{ and } t \text{ is any natural number greater than } 1.$$

Another way to resolve is to construct a new function, h , as follows:

$$h : P(N) \rightarrow N$$

$$h(\emptyset) = 2,$$

$$h(N) = 1, \text{ and for any other element } \{a, b, c, \dots\} \in P(N)$$

$$h(\{a, b, c, \dots\}) = 1 + t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots, \text{ where } a, b, c, \dots \in N, \text{ and } t \text{ is any natural number greater than } 1.$$

The issue with the “bad element” of the inverse function, g^{-1} , seems to disappear since $h^{-1}(1) = N$, but the “bad element” of h^{-1} now becomes $N - \{1\}$.

Of course, it is possible to construct another new function, k , such that

$$k : N \rightarrow P(N)$$

$$k(\emptyset) = 3,$$

$$k(N) = 1,$$

$$k(N - \{1\}) = 2, \text{ and for any other element } \{a, b, c, \dots\} \in P(N)$$

$$k(\{a, b, c, \dots\}) = 2 + t^a + t^b + t^c + \dots, \text{ where } a, b, c, \dots \in N, \text{ and } t \text{ is any natural number greater than } 1.$$

The construction of new functions like this can be continued as many times as possible, and the issue becomes similar to Hilbert's paradox of the Grand Hotel.

It is interesting to notice that \mathbf{N} has many subsets that contain infinite elements. The image values of these subsets under function, \mathbf{g} , are all infinite. For example, let $\mathbf{Z}_1, \mathbf{Z}_2 \in \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{N})$, and

$$\mathbf{Z}_1 = \mathbf{N} - \{1, 2\},$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_2 = \mathbf{N} - \{1, 2, 3\}.$$

Both $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{Z}_1)$ & $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{Z}_2)$ are infinite. One might, thus, argue that \mathbf{g} is not 1:1 since these different elements in $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{N})$ are all mapped to infinite. However, the difference in the image values between any 2 of these elements are always non-zero, e.g.

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{Z}_1) - \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{Z}_2) = \mathbf{t}^3, \text{ which proves that } \mathbf{g} \text{ is } 1:1.$$

Going back to the definition of function, \mathbf{g} , the main question is what infinite natural number, \mathbf{n} , can satisfy the following equation:

$$\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{t}^a + \mathbf{t}^b + \mathbf{t}^c + \dots \text{ when } \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \dots\} = \mathbf{N}.$$

This is also related to the question whether or not the infinite natural number is “any” natural number. In Mathematics, “any” natural numbers do not seem to include the infinite natural number. Nevertheless, in this case one can “always” find a natural number, $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{t}^a + \mathbf{t}^b + \mathbf{t}^c + \dots$, which belongs to the “any” natural numbers, such that $\mathbf{g}(\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \dots\}) = \mathbf{n}$ for “any” $\{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \dots\} \in \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{N})$. Thus, the cardinal number of $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{N})$ is less than or equal to that of \mathbf{N} . Some rethinking over the difference between “any” greater natural number and the infinite natural number might be necessary to reconcile the contradictory proof.

Cantor’s proof of none countable real numbers might be similar and needs to be cautious about.

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